

ISic4416

Epitaph for Philon, son Aunakos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

plinth

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited site

Last Change

2020-05-27 - Jonathan Prag created the file from template, publications, and photographs

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 69/70 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa , where it remains in situ

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Necropoli di Abakainon

Physical Description

Plinth (support for a stele) with mouldings top and bottom, of the local sandstone; the upper moulding is damaged, principally at the corners. The plinth is the right one of a pair mounted on a single base, classified as an epitombion of type C.

Dimensions

Height 33 cm

Width 60 cm

Depth 71 cm

Layout

Single line of greek letters approximately centred on the face of the plinth, descending to right

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Crude and irregularly carved large letters. Phi has a small eye, seemingly formed of two small loops; omega is small, mid-line, open, with outward/downward sloping tails; nu is large and uneven; alpha is broad, but the form of the bar is illegible; kappa has short equal arms joined to the vertical; omicron appears small and midline.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 59 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Φίλων Αβνακου

Apparatus

text based upon photographs

Sofia 2018: Φίλωνα[.]ἄκου

Translation (en)

Philon son of Aunakos

Commentary

The name Φίλων is extremely common; Αυνάκος on the other hand is only attested on the other plinth of this tomb, ISic4415 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4415>]. This plinth is one of a pair on a single base - a type attested several times in this necropolis - and the second plinth (ISic4415 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4415>]) is also inscribed and the presence of the name Αυνάκος in the genitive as its second element there suggests that the tomb is a double one for siblings. The same situation seems to be attested in the case of ISic4417 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4417>] / ISic4418 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4418>]. The first name here appears to be in the nominative (which has a parallel in ISic1208 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1208>]), rather than the more commonly found genitive in this necropolis. The lettering of this text is both larger and cruder than on the companion text, and less carefully set out, suggesting a different hand.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Bacci, G.M., Coppolino, P. 2009. La Necropoli di Abakainon: primi dati. Messina. At 28 fig.15 (and ref on p.113)
Sofia, G. 2018. Nuove iscrizioni funerarie dalla necropoli di Abakainon. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 206: 103-112. At 107 no.6 and fig.7

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